

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Reaction of Alcohols with HBr: A Case of Anchimeric Assistance by Hydroxyl group¹

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The kinetics of the reaction of monohydric alcohols and dihydric alcohols with HBr has been investigated. The first displacement in diols follows a regular order—ethylene glycol > propylene glycol > 1,3 butane diol > 1,4 butane diol. This is a first report of kinetics postulating the positive absence of inductive pull by the OH group but offering anchimeric assistance. Evidences have been presented to confirm the above mechanism by an independent study of 2-ethoxy- and 2-chloro-ethanols. The reaction is facilitated by electron releasing groups and with secondary alkyl groups there is a mixed mechanism, both unimolecular and bimolecular. The normal chain alcohols follow the same order as alkyl halides. A study of cyclic alcohols like cyclo-hexanol and 4-methyl-cyclo-hexanol also confirms the above postulates. The results can be rationalised on steric as well as polar effects. ρ value (-4.3) has been computed for the reaction with monohydric alcohols.

Bennett et al^{2,3} have studied the reaction of alcohols with HBr in aqueous phenol as solvent. The work does not throw much light on the structure and reactivity of either monohydric alcohols or dihydric alcohols in detail. It was found worth while to investigate this reaction thoroughly in a convenient solvent, glacial acetic acid. The main purpose of the investigation is to evaluate the rate constants of both the steps of displacement in diols.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials: The solvent used, glacial acetic acid, was purified by the usual procedure and distilled. The substrates used were of guaranteed quality or distilled before use.

The boiling points of the liquids used are as follows:

	Acetic Acid	118.1°		
Methanol	64.7°	Ethylene Glycol	197.9°	
Ethanol	78.4°	Propylene Glycol	189.0°	
Iso-Propanol	82.4°	1,3 Butane Diol	206.5°	
n-Butanol	118.0°	1,4 Butane Diol	230.0°	
2-Chloro-Ethanol	128.6°	Cyclo-Hexanol	161.1°	
2-Ethoxy-Ethanol	136.0°	4-Methyl Cyclo-Hexanol	174.0°	

Hydrobromic acid used is a freshly distilled azeotropic mixture (b. pt. 126°C),

The reactions are followed by the usual argentimetric procedure (Volhard's method).

1. Presented at the 54th Session of the Indian Science Congress, 1967, Hyderabad. Part III of the Proceedings, page 95.
2. G. M. Bennett and F. M. Reynolds, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 131.
3. G. M. Bennett and A. M. Mosses, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2956.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ethylene Glycol, Propylene Glycol and 1,3 Butane Diol: These were subjected to displacement by HBr expecting a consecutive second order process. It was intended to separate the rate constants of the first and second steps, and thus relate structure and reactivity.

The time ratios ($t_{60}/20$) in all cases were very high, for example:

$t_{60}/20$	Propylene Glycol	2,000
$t_{60}/20$	1,3 Butane Diol	200

which made it difficult to apply the Frost-Schwemer⁴ treatment. This incidentally indicated that both the steps are occurring at divergent velocities, one fairly fast and the other very slow. Stoichiometric ($A_0=2B_0$) experiments were conducted when after 50% conversion of the HBr, the reaction became sluggish. Experiments were conducted ($A_0=B_0$) to determine the rate of first displacement in the three cases. Excellent second order rate constants were obtained till even 40% of the process indicating no incursion of the second displacement. The subsequent displacement is so slow that it does not affect the first displacement.

Second order rate constant values of the 1st displacement

Solvent: glacial acetic acid		Temperature.....80°	
	Concentration of HBr	Concentration of the alcohol	K_1 1. moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
Ethylene glycol	.05845 M	.04718 M	5.93
Propylene glycol	.0577 M	.05645 M	2.349
1,3 Butane diol	.006465 M	.03265 M	0.2101

As the table indicates, the rate of first displacement in the three cases follows the order:

This is the first report of an order being followed in the above manner. The previous workers have reported a relative order.

Probably they were referring to the overall time taken cumulatively for the total displacement of both groups. It is evident that the second displacement makes the total reaction seemingly sluggish. In both the ethylene glycol and propylene glycol the second displacement is very sluggish and in 1,3 butane diol it is slow. Thus it requires a revision of the earlier ideas that ethylene glycol reacts slower than methanol. The first displacement is very fast compared to that of methanol but could be kinetically followed. The time taken for 20% conversion of the process is given below for comparative purposes:

Time for 20% Reaction

Solvent: Glacial Acetic Acid		Temperature.....80°	
	t_{20}		t_{20}
Methanol...	500	Propylene Glycol	1.8
Ethylene Glycol	1	1,3 Butane Diol	10.0

4. A. A. Frost and W. C. Schwemer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 1268.

Mechanism: The reaction consists of an attack by H^+ on the ethereal oxygen followed by Br^- attack on the nucleophilic carbon. It could occur depending on the substrate, by both unimolecular and bimolecular mechanisms, but kinetics cannot unequivocally establish which mechanism is operating⁵.

Bond fission seems much more significant than bond formation as electron releasing groups are favouring the reaction whereas electron withdrawing groups are retarding the process. 2-Chloro-ethanol is very slow confirming the above statement which is also in consonance with the electron attracting power of the substituent. It is well known that hydroxyl group in aliphatic systems is generally an electron attracting group which is exemplified by a comparison of the dissociation constants of acetic acid and glycolic acid⁶.

But in spite of the well known electron attracting power, the rate of the first displacement is very high with all the three substrates indicating some participation of adjacent or alternate hydroxyl in the transition state facilitating the loss of the other hydroxyl thus accelerating the process abnormally. This is a case of neighbouring group participation or anchimeric assistance leading to acceleration. From the rate constants it can be seen that ethylene glycol > propylene glycol > 1,3 butane diol, which is a pointer that assistance being offered by the adjacent hydroxyls is much better than alternate hydroxyls. It is not unreasonable to assume OH participation with compounds having adjacent hydroxyl groups as it is well known that ethylene chlorohydrins and substituted derivatives of ethylene chlorohydrins do undergo participation by adjacent OH. Now it becomes necessary to explain the differential activity of ethylene glycol *vs* propylene glycol. One could attribute the difference to the steric effect of the methyl group. Brown and co-workers have postulated similar arguments to explain the differential reactivity of methyl and ethyl chlorides⁷.

The negative oxygen in alkoxides is one of the most familiar neighbouring groups to participate leading to alkene oxides many of which are isolable. One of the very few unequivocal examples of hydroxyl participation is the ring closure of tetramethylene chlorohydrin in water to give tetrahydrofuran⁸. Most probably it is passing through the epoxide which is opened by Br^- . Even systems like $NH_2CH_2CH_2CH_2CH_2Br$ do undergo neighbouring group participation⁹. The probable course of the reaction in all diols and

5. C. K. Ingold, "Structure and Mechanism in Organic Chemistry", Bell G., 1963, pp. 340.

6. N. A. Lange, "Handbook of Chemistry", McGraw Hill, 1961.

7. M. S. Newman, "Steric Effects in Organic Chemistry", John Wiley, 1963, pp. 72.

8. E. S. Gould, "Mechanism and Structure in Organic Chemistry", Holt, Reinhardt and Winston, 1965, pp. 569.

9. *ibid*, pp. 570.

2-Ethoxy-Ethanol seems to be as follows:—

1,4 *Butane Diol*: Displacement reaction by HBr yielded time ratios which could be used to compute both the rate constants of the first and second steps. Frost-Schwemer treatment was applied and computation gave the following k_1 and k_2 :—

k_1 , l. moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	k_2 , l. moles ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	k_1/k_2
1.06×10^{-2}	1.97×10^{-3}	5.4

A comparison of k_1 with k_2 of 1,3 butane diol, propylene glycol and ethylene glycol reveals similarities.

Second order rate constants of the first displacement in diols

Solvent: glacial acetic acid	Concentration of HBr	Concentration of the diol	Temperature.....80°	k_1 l. mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
1,4 Butane diol	.05955 M	.02996 M		1.063×10^{-2}
1,3 Butane diol	.06465 M	.03265 M		2.101×10^{-1}
Propylene glycol	.05770 M	.05645 M		2.349
Ethylene glycol	.05845 M	.04718 M		5.93

As the separation of OH's increases k_1 decreases. This shows that OH is not acting inductively as is understood generally in aliphatic systems. OH is participating to assist the displacement of OH_2^+ . As the distance increases the capacity to participate in the assistance decreases as is shown by the values. It is clear that OH is offering anchimeric assistance in all the cases. The second step is certainly slow as Br that is present inductively acts and retards the rate. This is quite established with a separate run with 2-chloro-ethanol, under similar conditions.

	k_1 , l. mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
2-Chloro-Ethanol	1.06×10^{-3}

2-Ethoxy-Ethanol: To establish the neighbouring group participation by OH a separate run was done with 2-ethoxy-ethanol under similar conditions. This also underwent substitution at a rate much higher than ethanol in spite of the classical -J_s effect of the ethoxy group. But its value when compared to ethylene glycol (1st displacement) is very low indicating that in the participation OH acts much more easily than OC_2H_5 , probably due to the shielding of the ethyl in the ethoxy group.

	k_1 , l. mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
Ethanol	3.72×10^{-3}
2-Ethoxy-Ethanol	1.80×10^{-2}
Ethylene Glycol	5.93*

*1st displacement

Mono-Hydric alcohols: The following are the rate constants obtained with mono-hydric alcohols like methanol, ethanol, 2-propanol and n-butanol:

Second order rate Constants of Monohydric Alcohols

Solvent: glacial acetic acid	Concentration of HBr	Concentration of the alcohol	Temperature 50° k _l l. mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
Methanol	.06063 M	.05610M	9.41×10 ⁻³
Ethanol	.05196 M	.05240M	3.72×10 ⁻³
iso-Propanol	.05950 M	.05565M	5.33×10 ⁻³
n-butanol	.05770 M	.04970M	2.57×10 ⁻³

As is clear from the table the increase in chain length retards the process in normal alcohols. The order is:

This is quite in consonance with the behaviour of these substituent groups in other reactions. The origin may be steric or polar or both. δ value has been computed and it has a value of 4.3. This is the first report of a δ value for this displacement process which is quite reasonable for bimolecular reactions.

In the case of 2-propanol there is mixed mechanism both unimolecular and bimolecular kinetically indistinguishable. The high value is attributed to the incursion of the uni-process.

Cyclic Alcohols: A comparison of 20% conversion in cyclo-hexanol and 4-methyl-cyclohexanol reveals that the electron releasing groups favour the substitution in consonance with the above postulate for monohydric alcohols. Further experiments are under progress to relate the conformation and reactivity.

	t_{20} min	t_{25} min	t_{30} min
Cyclo-hexanol	1,785	2,225	2,700
4-Methyl Cyclo-hexanol	513	870	1,380

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